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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF PRESCRIPTIONS FOR VARIOUS EFFECTS OF
POLY PHARMACY IN TERTIARY HOSPITAL CARE**

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Abstract:

Every patient on an average these days takes multiple prescriptions if he is suffering from single or multiple diseases. This practice of taking multiple drugs is called polypharmacy. The therapy might be a combination or polytherapy which is sometimes used for single diseased condition. Polypharmacy may be deleterious because of increased concomitant symptoms and drug interactions. These noxious results might cause the patient readmission at hospital. Recently many researchers have come forward on how to make effects of polypharmacy less morbid. In the present research, a retrospective and prospective study conducted at Yashoda Hospital, Secunderabad, Telangana for a period of 6 months collected 196 prescriptions from patients ranging from (age range). This data was used to identify the prevalence of polypharmacy among the survey population. The goal of present study is to provide a detail observational study on the patients and related consequences occurred by polypharmacy.

Key Words: Prescriptions, poly pharmacy, noxious, symptoms, readmissions.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Vasudha Bakshi**

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INTRODUCTION:

A recent study brings home the incidence of poly pharmacy in the homebound elderly. Published in the Journal of the American Geriatrics Society in August 1999, the study looked at the drug consumption of 2,193 individuals over the age of 60 who lived at home. The conclusions of this study revealed a high prevalence of inappropriate drug use in the older home bound adult. The study looked at 527 men and 1,666 women with an average age of 83 years. The average number of prescriptions per person was 5.3 and there was no difference between men and women. Ten percent of the drugs prescribed were on the inappropriate drug list--usually due to a potential for an adverse reaction or because a better choice is available. At least 39.7 percent of those polled had at least one prescription for an inappropriate drug, and 10.4 percent had two or more prescriptions for an inappropriate drug. The study shows that the elderly are at greatest risk for poly pharmacy and even at the risk of adverse drug reaction.

METHODOLOGY:

Poly pharmacy patients of both the sexes of different age groups included in the study. These studies were conducted to evaluate the best approaches to reduce the poly pharmacy. This study aims to counsel the patients for the better life and effective

Study site

This study was conducted in General department of Yashoda Hospital, Secunderabad, Telangana, India.

Plan of work

Figure 1: Scheme of work

Study period

This study was proposed to be conducted for 6 months from December 2015 to may 2016.

Study design

A prospective observational study.

Subject criteria**Inclusion criteria**

- Patients with multiple diseases.
- Inpatients were included
- Elderly people

Exclusion criteria

- Pediatrics
- Pregnant women

Procedure

- Designing the patient profile form.
- Seeking permission from the Ethical Committee.
- Diagnosis of patients with multiple co morbidities and their symptoms.
- Identify the patients prescribed with multiple medications.
- Collection of data.
- Grouping the data based on sex, type of dosage forms, age groups.
- Assessing the prescription pattern of the patients.
- Evaluation of the best applicable therapy for the patient
- Statistical evaluation of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Statistical analysis****Demographic details of the patients****Total no. of cases based on age as criteria**

Out of 194 cases, the based on the criteria given by NHS Scotland, the people of above the age group of 65 years where considered to be included, the patients include 76 and number of the patients excluded are 118.

Table 1: Age criteria

Age criteria	No. of patients	Percentages
(Poly pharmacy) Patients above 65years of age	76	39
(Non poly pharmacy) Patients below 60 years of age	118	61

Figure 2: Age criteria**Total no. of cases considering on usage of multiple medications as criteria**

Out of 194 cases, 76 were included in the criteria of the poly pharmacy, from these patients were segregated into different categories on intake on medications. The patients which intake of medicines more than 10 were, 46 in number and patients with intake of more 5 drugs were 20 in number and intake of 5 drugs were 10 in number.

Table 2: Prescribed number of medicines

Usage of medicinations	No. of patients	Percentages
Patients prescribed with more than 10 drugs	46	60
Patients prescribed with more than 5 drugs	12	16
Patients prescribed with 5 drugs	18	24

Figure 3: Prescribed number of medicines

Table 3: Total no. of cases were patients with multiple diseased conditions are considered as criteria

Count of diseases	No. of patients	Percentages
More than 3 diseases	38	56
Patients with 2 diseases	30	44

Figure 4: Count of diseases**Based on sex**

Total of 76 patients there are 46 male patients and 30 female patients enrolled into the study while considering the both inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 4: No. of patients based on sex

S. No.	Sex	No. of patients	Percentage
1.	Male	46	60
2.	Female	30	40

Figure 5: Sex ratio**Based on the total number of category of drugs**

Through this study, the total count of medicines prescribed were 1903, of these 12% medicines are antibiotics, 1% are antacids, vitamin supplements are 9.19%, antipyretics 6.88%, anti emetics 5.73%, anti inflammatory 4.05%, anti hypertensives 4.78%, analgesics 3.94%, laxatives 3.99%, anti convulsants 2.52%, anti coagulants 2.52%, anti histamines 1.94% these were the drug category which were mostly prescribed in all cases and others category of drugs include 30%.

Table 5: Antibiotics

CATEGORY	CLASS OF DRUGS	REPEATS	PERCENTAGES
Antibiotics	Oxazolidinones	6	7
	Ansamycins	1	1.2
	Aminoglycosides	6	7
	Polypeptides	6	7
	Fluoroquinolones	6	7
	Carbapenems	6	7
	Nitrofurans	6	7
	Tetracyclines	6	7
	Lincosamides	3	3.4
	Cephalosporins	6	7
	Macrolides	6	7
	Glycopeptides	6	7
	Sulphonamides	6	7
	Others antibiotics	6	7
	Penicillin combinations	6	7

Figure 6: Antibiotics**Table 6: Anti emetics**

CATEGORY	DRUGS	REPEATS	PERCENTAGES
Anti emetics	Ondansetron	94	95
	Dimenhydrate	1	1
	Ondansetron HCl	1	1
	Domperidone	1	1
	Cinitapride	1	1
	Aprepitant	1	1

Figure 7: Anti emetics

Table 7: Anti pyretics

CATEGORY	DRUGS	REPEATS	PERCENTAGES
Anti pyretics	Paracetamol	37	48
	Acetaminophen	38	49
	Paracetamol.methionine	2	3

Figure 8: Anti pyretics

Table 8: Analgesics

CATEGORY	DRUGS	REPEATS	PERCENTAGES
Analgesics	Epidural analgesic	2	6
	Tramadol	20	57
	Lidocaine HCl	1	2.8
	Tramadol/pcm	1	2.8
	Tramadol HCl/acetaminophen	10	29
	Flupirtine	1	2.8

Figure 9: Analgesics

Table 9: Antacids

CATEGORY	DRUGS	REPEATS	PERCENTAGES
Antacids	Pantoprazole	27	77.1
	Esomeprazole	1	3
	Rebamipide	1	3
	Bacillus clausii	1	3
	Sucralfate	1	3
	Rabeprazole	1	3
	Simethicone	1	3
	Rabeprazole	1	3
	Famotidine	1	3

Figure 10: Antacids

Table 10: Anti coagulants

Category	Drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Anti coagulants	Enoxaparin sodium	5	42
	Rivoroxaban	1	8.3
	Warfarin	1	8.3
	Heparin	1	8.3
	Dalteparin	1	8.3
	Acenocoumarol	1	8.3
	Nicomalon	1	8.3

Figure 11: Anti coagulants**Table 11: Anti coagulants**

Category	Drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Anti platelets	Chlordiazepoxide	5	38.4
	Escitalopram	1	8
	Alprazolam	3	23
	Hydroxyzline	1	8
	Lorazepam	2	15.3
	Clonazepam	1	8

Figure 12: Anti coagulants

Table 12: Anti histamines

Category	Class of drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Anti histamines	H1 antagonists	20	87
	H1 reverse agonists	1	4.3
	H2 antagonist	2	8.7

Figure 13: Anti histamines**Table 13: Laxatives**

Category	Drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Laxatives	Lactulose	10	50
	Ispaghula husk+lactilol monohydrate	1	5
	Paraffin+magnesium hydroxide	5	25
	Macrogol	1	5
	Bisacodyl	1	5
	Lactitol monohydrate	2	10

Figure 14: Laxatives

Table 14: Vitamins

Category	Class of drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Vitamins	Vitamin B	20	61
	Vitamin E	1	3
	Multivitamin	6	18
	Vitamin D	1	3
	Lycostar	1	3
	Oncovit	1	3
	Vitamin K	1	3
	Vitamin A/B	1	3
	Vitamin B/C	1	3

Figure 15: Vitamins

Table 15: Anti inflammatory agents

Category	Class of drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Anti inflammatory drugs	Propionic acid derivatives	3	15
	Enolic acid derivatives	1	5
	Anthranilic acid derivatives	1	5
	Acetic acid derivatives	9	45
	Salicylates	5	25
	Selective cox-2	1	5

Figure 16: Anti inflammatory agents

Table 16: Anti convulsants

Category	Drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Anti convulsants	Gabapentin	5	22
	Pregablin	5	22
	Levetiracetam	5	22
	Divaiproex	1	4
	Midazolam	2	9
	Topiramate	1	4
	Phenytoin	3	13
	Clonazepam	1	4

Figure 17: Anti convulsants**Table 17: Anti hypertensives**

Category	Drugs	Repeats	Percentages
Anti hypertensive drugs	Amlodipine	7	23
	Telmisartan	6	19
	Losartan	2	6.4
	Metoprolol	1	3.2
	Clonidine	1	3.2
	Prazosin	2	6.4
	Olmesartan	1	3.2
	Clinidipine	1	3.2
	Carvedilol	1	3.2
	Perindopril	1	3.2
	Atenolol	2	6.4
	Labetolol	1	3.2
	Moxonidine	1	3.2
	Ramipril	1	3.2
	Hydrochlorothiazide	1	3.2
	Clinidipine	1	3.2
	Enalapril	1	3.2

Figure 18: Anti hypertensives

Table 18: Other drugs

Category	Total no. of repeats	Percentages
Bronchodilators	11	1.4
Anti depressants	3	0.3
Anti diarrhoeals	3	0.3
Hypothyroids	3	0.3
Hyperthyroids	1	0.0
Steroids	13	2
Hypotensives	2	0.2
Treat bronchospasm	3	0.3
Anti histamines	23	3
Anti tussives	5	0.7
Diuretics	23	3.1
Treat anaemia	6	0.8
Anti convulsants	23	3.1
Anti malarials	9	1.2
Anti helminthics	5	0.7
Anti diabetics	11	1.4
Anti tuberculars	13	2
Anti flatulents	5	0.7
Anti psychotics	12	2
Appetite enhancers	1	0.0
Treat hypokalemia	3	0.3
Anti anxiety	6	0.8
Anti asthma and COPD	2	0.2
Anti histamine and anti asthma	7	0.9
Treat hyper phosphatemia	7	0.9
Gout treatment	3	0.3
Optic drugs	2	0.2
Anti parkinson	3	0.3
Treat Alzheimers	12	1.6
Anti platelets	13	2
Anti hyperlipidemics	4	0.5
Alpha blockers	3	0.3
Anti arrhythmatics	2	0.2

Urinary anti spasmodics	5	0.7
Anti spasmodics	4	0.5
Local anaesthetic	4	0.5
Skeletal muscle relaxant	9	1.2
Anti virals	3	0.3
Anti septics	1	0.1
Mucolytic agent	5	0.7
Anti cholelithic	1	0.1
Treat osteoporosis	2	0.2
Cancer treatment	5	0.7
Digestives enzymes	2	0.2
Amino acids	1	0.1
Anti fungals	5	0.7
Angina drugs	4	0.5
Treat haemorrhoids	2	0.2
Treat hyponatremia	1	0.1
Anti fibrolytics	2	0.2
Analegsic/ anti inflammatory	1	0.1
Treat osteoarthritis	1	0.1

Figure 19: Other drugs

Table 19: Graph based on the diseased conditions prevailing in patient

Diseased conditions	No. of the patients	Percentages
CKD Patients	14	36
CLD Patients	12	31
Cardiac patients	6	15
Orthopaedic patients	7	18

Figure 20: Count of patients on disease condition

Table 20: Graph on the repeated medications and drug interactions

		Percentages
Repeated doses	30	3.94
Drugs interactions	15	1.97

Out of the 76 patients, 760 drugs were prescribed merely, and in few of the cases there were drugs of repeated doses and drugs- drug interactions were noted.

Figure 21: Data analysis

CONCLUSION:

The inference from my study is that though poly pharmacy mainly leads with lot of medicines prescribing, which may be beneficial or may be harmful do to repeated doses or drug interactions. As this study on poly pharmacy is under develop because there are still a controversial discussion hence as it cannot be completed put the mistake on the doctors or pharmacist or the patients, the best way for the reducing of the poly pharmacy is mainly by either assessing and reducing the dose of the drugs or number of prescribed drugs to prevent further effects.

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